

SOUND ABSORPTION OF ELECTROSPUN POLYVINYLIDENE FLUORIDE/CARBON NANOTUBE MEMBRANES

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ABSTRACT

Piezoelectric polymers based on polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) are of interest for the tactile sensor arrays, strain gauges and audio transducers applications. When a piezoelectric material is subjected to stress or force, it generates an electrical potential or voltage proportional to the magnitude of the force. This makes this type of transducer ideal as a converter of mechanical energy or force into electric potential. A piezoelectric audio transducer can convert sound pressure into electric voltage, and vice versa. Thus, reduction of vibrations and noise may be achieved by piezoelectric material.

In this study, a novel sound-absorbing material was developed by using electrospun piezoelectric PVDF membranes. The influence of carbon nanotube (CNT) added and the electrospinning (ES) process on the crystal structure and piezoelectric properties of PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes were examined. Results show that electrospinning is an effective method to induce β -phase significantly and enhances the piezoelectricity. Addition of CNT further improves the piezoelectric properties and can be explained by the concept of interfacial polarization. ES nanofiber membranes enhance the surface area and contribute more sound waves contact which result in more sound energy absorption in middle frequency region by the friction and vibration. The piezoelectric ES PVDF samples played an important role in converting the sound energy to electric potential and absorbed the sound wave in low frequency region. The ES PVDF/CNT membranes with the highest piezoelectricity and thus shifts the sound absorption to lower frequency region. The ES PVDF/acoustic foam has a potential to be widely used as an efficient sound absorber in practical situations because of its good absorption performance in particular at low and middle frequency.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, in order to enhance the quality of life for people, the noise control problem has attracted widespread attention from governments and technology workers. Noise is mainly controlled from two parts. First, we can let the volume become lower or turn off it. This is the quickly and thoroughly way. Second way is to develop various kinds of structure for sound-absorbing materials.

Sound wave was a kind of mechanical wave. It was similar to fluctuation of light or electromagnetic wave had reflection, transmission and absorption [1]. Fiber mat as a porous material was a good sound-absorbing material which had loose structure and many interface. As sound strikes porous or fibrous materials, the sound waves would contact with the surface and even had some friction between the pores. It would produce heat loss due to friction when the sound wave crosses the irregular pores, thus decrease the strength of noise and change its transmission route [2].

Some of the noise absorbers were used on aircraft interior. On the market, porous absorbers include mineral wool, plastic foams, textiles, cotton and special acoustic plaster. Asmatulu used PVC nanofiber membranes to absorb the sound [3]. He showed that high surface area flexible micron and nanofibers could absorb the sound better than conventionally used micro scale sound absorbers. It is therefore concluded that these high surface area micro and nanofibers can be used as alternative

materials to reduce the interior noise of the aircrafts. Therefore, the applications of fiber mat could achieve sound absorption for noise control.

Currently, Kundu and Berry used piezoelectric material to convert the sound wave into electric energy for sound absorption material development [4]. When sound wave strikes material, it would had vibration and friction. The piezoelectric material could convert vibration into electric energy. Therefore, piezoelectric material could be energy acquisition and a new application on sound absorption. Generally, piezoelectric materials were divided into four forms: crystal type, film type, ceramics type and polymer type [5]. Polymeric piezoelectric materials like Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) was widely investigated due to their conformable nature provide their application on complex structural surfaces. They are lightweight, high-strength, conformable, and can be cut into different shapes/sizes. Furthermore, their polymeric nature and chemical compatibility allows precise tailoring of the material using other nanomaterial species.

PVDF had five crystalline phases with different conformations, namely: (1) all-trans (TTTT) planar zigzag for β -phase, (2) TGTG' for α and δ phases, and (3) T₃GT₃G' for γ and ϵ phases [6]. The non-polar α phase was most commonly found in commercially available films. The β phase has dipole moments pointing in the same direction; thus, the β phase was responsible for the piezoelectric properties of PVDF polymer [7,8]. The polar β -phase could be obtained through various post-treatments such as mechanical stretching and high electric field poling [9]. Liu used electrospinning system to polarize PVDF from α phase to β phase. It was a simple way to obtain β phase and shown better polarization than mechanical stretching [10].

Carbon nanotubes (CNT) have been widely employed because of their large aspect ratio and high surface area. These physical attributes render them ideal candidates for chemical functionalization and for embedding electromechanical and electrochemical sensing transduction mechanisms within one composite film structure. The resulting multifunctional nanocomposite thin film can then be applied onto virtually any structural surface for sensing/actuation without interfering with structural performance and functionality. The PVDF/CNT composite showed remarkably enhanced ferro-, pyro-, and piezoelectric properties when the carbon nanotubes were well dispersed. Nanocomposites made from PVDF and CNTs have the potential to be smart materials, not only because of the combination of the piezoelectric properties of PVDF and the conducting properties of CNTs, but also because of the higher levels of β -phase formation in the electrospun nanofibers and thus the better piezoelectric properties [11]. Interfacial polarization arises for electrically heterogeneous materials, i.e. composites of different conductive materials such as CNTs-polymer composites. Mobile charge within the conductive phase (CNTs) can facilitate polarization of the composites. Therefore, interfacial polarization results in an increase in the dielectric constant [12].

Electrospinning (ES) process was a straightforward way to continuously fabricate the nanofibers or web and could provide a high orientation. In ES system, a highly surface-charged polymeric solution at high flow rate and, which was maintained in a hemispherical geometry right at ES needle, could be extended, deformed and spurted to the collector under an applied electrical field [13].

Kalinov'a had shown that ES nanofiber was kind of porous fibrous material and could be a highly efficient sound absorber [14]. It consisted of higher surface area, porosity and flexibility, which in turn could enhance the absorption rate of the noise more than conventional materials like non-woven and acoustic foam [3]. While the nanofibers' characteristics were determined by molecular weight, viscosity, surface tension, conductivity, electric field, distance between the needle and the collector. These parameters would influence the morphology of electrospun nanofibers and sound-absorbing frequency region [15]. Moreover, he also pointed out that the frequency of nanofiber would shift to lower region along with increasing area density of the nanofiber membrane [16]. Not only increased the effect of high-frequency absorption but also improved low and middle frequency absorption capacity.

Generally, the conventional materials like non-woven and acoustic foam could absorb the universal voice at high-frequency region. But as noise problem, middle and low frequency were more damage for our healthy. Developing various kinds of structure for sound-absorbing materials was becoming important issue. The purpose of this study was using ES process to polarize PVDF materials for good piezoelectric property. Then we added some conductive materials to improve the piezoelectric property. The piezoelectric PVDF nanofibers might convert the sound energy into a different energy

types such as electric currents. Therefore, porous PVDF materials were prepared by ES process, and the effects of piezoelectric properties on the sound-absorbing would be studied.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

PVDF film (Solef[®] 1010), purchased from Solvay Co., U.S.A, was used in this study. PVDF pellets (Kynar[®]720) with a molecular weight of 263,000 were purchased from Arkema Group, France for ES process. Multiwall CNTs were purchased from Golden Innovation Business Company, Taiwan. ITO/PET with sheet resistivity of 200 Ω /sq. and thickness of 0.13 mm, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich was used as the substrate for ES process.

2.2 Preparation of the ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes

PVDF solution was prepared by adding 2.2 g of PVDF pellets into 6 ml of DMF solution and stirring gently at a temperature of approximately 100°C for 2 hours. The suspended CNT/DMF solution (0.5 wt%) was sonicated for 20 mins at 40 Hz by an ultrasonic cell disrupter machine. Then, 0.5 ml suspended CNT/DMF solution was added into the as prepared PVDF solution at 100°C under stirring, and then cooling down to room temperature. The PVDF/CNT solution (18 wt%) for ES process was prepared by adding 4 ml acetone into the as-prepared PVDF/CNT solution for better evaporation.

An in-house designed ES device consisting of an injection spinneret powered by a syringe pump (KDS 101 Series, Kd scientific, U.S.A.) connected to a Teflon tube attached to a stainless steel needle (0.31 mm diameter), acting as the spinneret. An electrostatic controller (SM 4030-24NIR, You-Shang Technical Corp., Taiwan), connected to the spinneret and the collector, was grounded. The ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes were directly electrospun and deposited onto the ITO/PET substrate under the following ES conditions: applied voltage 20 kV, working distance 20 cm, flowing rate 0.5 ml/hr.

Besides, for comparison, PVDF film samples with (stretching ratio: 3.5) or without stretched were prepared.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology of the ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes were analyzed by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6390, Japan) and operated at 20 kV.

A universal test machine (QC-508M2, Comotech, Taiwan) was used to perform the tensile test for ES PVDF nanofiber membranes at room temperature according to ASTM D882. Dumbbell specimens with gauge lengths of 33 mm and widths of 6 mm were prepared for each tensile test. The crosshead speed was 50 mm/min. All the tensile properties reported represent the average value of at least five readings.

During DSC analysis, the ES PVDF nanofiber membranes were ramped from 25°C to 230°C at a rate of 20°C/min, then maintained at isothermal conditions for 3 minutes at 230°C. The ES PVDF nanofiber membranes were then cooled at a rate of 20°C/min to ambient. The nominal melting temperature (T_m) was defined as the peak of the melting endotherm during first heating from 25°C to 230°C, and the nominal crystallization temperature (T_c) was defined as the peak of the crystallization exothermally upon cooling from 230°C to 25°C. The X-Ray diffraction (XRD, D2 Phaser, Bruker, Germany) was performed at a scanning rate of 0.4 °/sec from $2\theta=10^\circ$ to 40° . Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR, FTS-1000, Digilab, U.S.A.) were recorded over a range of 1500-650 cm^{-1} wavenumber with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

The sound-absorbing coefficient of ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes were calculated under the conditions of ASTM E1050-08, as shown Figure 1. The sample was carefully placed in the sample holder and made sure sample surface be flat with respect to the sound wave propagation direction. The power amplifier would give a signal to speaker (sound source), and then the speaker released the sound to bumped sample. The two fixed-spacing microphones could measure the sound pressure

between speaker and sample. The values of sound pressure would transfer to data acquisition unit, and then we could obtain sound-absorbing coefficient through computer.

Figure 1. The impedance measurement of sound-absorbing coefficient.

The two-microphone impedance measurement consists of 99.8 mm diameter impedance tube (large tube) and 30.4 mm diameter impedance tube (small tube), as shown Figure 2. The impedance tube is used to measure the acoustic absorption and reflection coefficients of any test samples in the frequency range of 80 Hz to 6.4 kHz. Large-tube (low frequency) setup to measure the parameters in the frequency range 80 Hz to 1.6 kHz, and a small-tube (high frequency) setup for frequency range from 1kHz to 6.4 kHz.

Figure 2. The impedance tube for two diameters: (1) was 99.8 mm diameter impedance tube, (2) was 30.4 mm diameter impedance tube, (3) was placement for sample.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Morphology of ES PVDF/CNT Nanofibers Membranes

The diameter of ES PVDF nanofibers was strongly influenced by the viscosity and dielectric of ES fluid and applied electrical field, etc. Figure 3(a) and 3(b) show SEM images of ES PVDF without and with CNT nanofiber membrane, and their average fiber diameter were in the range of 156 ± 13 nm and 138 ± 21 nm, respectively. Thinner nanofibers were obtained in ES PVDF/CNT samples comparing to ES PVDF. Figure 3(c) and 3(d) show TEM images of ES PVDF without and with CNT nanofiber membrane. The PVDF nanofibers' surface is rough under large magnification. Some CNTs were embedded within PVDF nanofibers are clear shown in Figure 3(d). The large surface areas of ES PVDF nanofiber membranes with and without CNT were thus prepared successfully.

Figure 3. The SEM of (a) ES PVDF, (b) ES PVDF/CNT, and TEM of (c) ES PVDF (d) ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membrane.

3.2 The Tensile Property of ES PVDF Nanofiber Membranes

The representative tensile stress–strain curves of the ES PVDF nanofiber membranes are shown in Figure 4. The modulus and tensile strength of ES PVDF/CNT are superior to ES PVDF. Both stress–strain curves display significant yielding and strain hardening. It is because of the de-entanglement of the nanofiber webs and orientation of the nanofibers. ES PVDF/CNT exhibits an average tensile strength (4.2 MPa) more than six-fold that of ES PVDF (0.7 MPa). Similar, ES PVDF/CNT exhibits a tensile modulus (17.2 MPa) more than seven-fold that of ES PVDF (2.5 MPa). The increase in tensile strength and modulus can be attributed to the alterations in the polymer microstructure produced by electrospinning and poling [12] and to the presence of high tenacity CNTs well incorporated within the PVDF nanofibers as is evident from Figure 3(d). As a result, the PVDF nanofiber and its fiber membrane’s mechanical properties were dramatically improved. ES PVDF exhibits lower tensile strength and modulus than ES PVDF/CNT but ES PVDF has a higher elongation at break.

Figure 4. Tensile stress-strain curves of ES PVDF nanofiber membranes.

3.3 The Crystallinity Property of ES PVDF Nanofiber Membranes

DSC, XRD and FTIR were utilized to evaluate the extent of β -phase in PVDF. The melting/crystallization temperatures observed upon the heating and the subsequent cooling of the PVDF membranes are shown in Figure 5, shows sequence thermograms of ES PVDF and ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes. Double melting peaks were shown in the 1st heating endothermograms of the two samples. Melting peak at 171 °C corresponding to melting of α -phase crystalline where as peaks at 169.5 °C and 168.7 °C was contributed by melting of β -phase which induced by ES process. It is noteworthy that another high melting peak at 179 °C which may be the γ -phase crystalline was found in ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes and resulted from the heterogeneous nucleation and crystallization caused by CNT [17]. The glass transition temperature, T_g , are 52.6 °C for ES PVDF and 63.2 °C for ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes with 10.6 °C increasing. It is proved that PVDF/CNT presents strong physical interaction between CNT and PVDF molecular chains and thus restricts the motion of PVDF molecules [18]. As shown in the cooling exothermograms of the two samples, PVDF with CNT was crystallized at 139.6 °C, while sample without CNT was 131.6 °C. The crystallization temperature, T_c , increasing is attributed to the heterogeneous nucleation induced by the CNT and revealed a strong interaction between CNT and PVDF molecules. As for the heat of fusion, they are 65.1 J/g for melting and 61.0 J/g for crystallization in the ES PVDF samples, while ES PVDF/CNT samples shown 52.5 J/g for melting and 51.8 J/g for crystallization. The existence of CNTs might hinder crystallization of the PVDF matrix during solidification [18].

Figure 5. DSC thermograms of ES PVDF nanofiber membranes.

XRD patterns of various PVDF samples are shown in Figure 6. Unstretched PVDF film shows diffraction peak at $2\theta = 18.6^\circ$, 20.3° , and 27.0° are reflections of α phase at (020), (110) and (021) [19]. The diffraction peak at 20.6° as shown in the stretched PVDF film, ES PVDF and ES PVDF/CNT samples is reflection of β -phase at (110), which proved α/β phase coexisted in the ES and stretched samples. A strong diffraction peak was found at $2\theta = 29.5^\circ$ for ES PVDF/CNT samples, is (002) reflection of CNT and prove CNT was dispersed with the PVDF nanofibers [20]. Based on the diffraction peak intensity, we know ES PVDF displays the highest β -phase fraction, follow by ES PVDF/CNT and stretched samples, while unstretched samples exhibit the lowest β -phase fraction.

Figure 6. XRD results for various PVDF samples.

FTIR was employed to quantify the variation of the PVDF crystal phase. Figure 7 showed the FTIR spectra for the four PVDF samples. Based on the resulted FTIR spectra, the α phase is resolved at 765, 795 and 975 cm^{-1} and the β -phase at 840 and 1278 cm^{-1} [21]. Obviously, we found clear β -phase at the samples of stretched, ES PVDF and ES PVDF/CNT.

Figure 7. FTIR spectra for various PVDF samples.

The relative β -phase fraction of PVDF samples, $F(\beta)$, was estimated using the FTIR absorption which was assumed to follow the Lambert-Beer law [21]. $F(\beta)$ in a sample containing formula could be written as Equation 1:

$$F(\beta) = \frac{X_{\beta}}{X_{\alpha} + X_{\beta}} = \frac{A_{\beta}}{\left(\frac{K_{\beta}}{K_{\alpha}}\right)A_{\alpha} + A_{\beta}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{α} and A_{β} were the ratios of incident and absorbed intensity at 765 and 840 cm^{-1} , respectively, and the constant factor 1.3 was obtained from the absorption coefficient rate K_{β}/K_{α} at the corresponding wavenumber. According to this equation, we calculated the value of $F(\beta)$ as follow: unstretched PVDF film was 14%, stretched PVDF film was 52%, ES PVDF was 83% and ES PVDF/CNT was 70%. Therefore, we can conclude that ES process is an effective method to induce β -phase significantly. Besides, it is reported that the addition of the CNTs induced charge accumulation at the boundary, which helped the PVDF chains to become arranged in the β -phase conformation [11]. The existence of CNTs might hinder crystallization of the PVDF matrix during solidification and thus reduced the β -phase transformation which agrees to the DSC results.

3.4 The Piezoelectric Property of ES PVDF/CNT Nanofiber Membranes

We used piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} meter to test the relationship between crystallization and piezoelectric property. First, we let the sample be sandwiched into the fixture of d_{33} meter. Then we could turn on the d_{33} meter and obtain the piezoelectric coefficient. Table 1 showed the value of $F(\beta)$ and piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} . Unstretched PVDF film was 10.5, stretched PVDF film was 11.7, ES PVDF was 15.2 and ES PVDF/CNT was 18.8. It was 1.2 times increasing with stretched PVDF film. Hence, the ES process was helpful for crystallization on β phase. Piezoelectric coefficient would increase with relative fraction of β phase. PVDF with CNT exhibits the highest piezoelectric coefficient, even though the fraction of β phase is not high enough. Less crystallinity may result in a reduced dielectric constant. However, results show CNT/PVDF demonstrated higher piezoelectric coefficient. The results prove that mobile charge within the conductive phase (CNTs) can facilitate polarization of the composites and thus the interfacial polarization arises for electrically heterogeneous materials. The tendency for polarization can be enhanced by adjusting the permittivity or dielectric constant of the piezoelectric PVDF polymer by incorporating a conductive CNT phase within the nanofibers [12]. These increases of piezoelectricity can be explained by the concept of interfacial polarization between the embedded CNTs phase and the polymer matrix.

Sample	$F(\beta)$	d_{33}
unstretched PVDF film	14%	10.5
stretched PVDF film	52%	11.7
ES PVDF	83%	15.2
ES PVDF/CNT	70%	18.8

Table 1. The value of $F(\beta)$ and piezoelectric coefficient for various PVDF samples.

3.5 The Sound-absorbing coefficient of ES PVDF/CNT Nanofiber Membranes

Samples of nanofiber membranes and nanofiber membrane attached onto acoustic foam were prepared and their sound-absorbing coefficients were evaluated. First, we cut the samples into tested size, as shown in Figure 8 and determined the area density (g/m^2). The area densities of samples are unstretched PVDF film: 156.3 g/m^2 , stretched PVDF film: 97.6 g/m^2 , ES PVDF: 39.1 g/m^2 , ES PVDF/CNT: 45.5 g/m^2 and ES PVA: 48.3 g/m^2 . The sound-absorbing coefficients of the PVDF samples were shown in Figure 9. In middle frequency region, we compared ES products with PVDF films, and found that all of ES products could absorb sound more than PVDF films. After that, we focus on low frequency region and compared PVDF series products with ES PVA. We found that PVDF products could absorb low frequency than ES PVA, and their frequency were about at 160Hz. Besides, we also found that the frequency of ES PVDF/CNT could shift to lower region and the frequency of ES PVDF/CNT was located about at 100 Hz. Hence, this result showed us that ES products could absorb the sound in middle frequency (315-1250 Hz) region. Piezoelectric materials could absorb the sound in low frequency (50-250 Hz) region. The results could be attributed to the use of piezoelectric shunt damping which can reduce the sound transmission of PVDF membranes at low resonant frequencies [22]. The addition of the CNTs improves the piezoelectric properties of PVDF membrane and thus further shifts the sound absorbing frequency to lower region.

Figure 8. Materials for sound-absorbing measurement, (a) ES PVDF, (b) ES PVA, (c) unstretched PVDF film and (d) stretched PVDF film.

Figure 9. Sound-absorbing coefficient for various PVDF samples.

For practical applications, ES PVDF nanofiber membrane was attached onto acoustic foam, as shown in Figure 10. Based on the impedance tube measurement, we obtained the sound-absorbing coefficient as shown in Figure 11. This component not only keep original sound-absorbing coefficient at 100 Hz but also increased dramatically sound-absorbing capability at middle region. Moreover, the sound-absorbing coefficient of ES PVDF foam sample at middle region could reach the highest coefficient about 0.8, whereas ES PVDF/CNT foam sample even higher to value of 0.9. The sound-absorbing coefficient at low frequency region for ES PVDF/CNT foam sample exhibit the highest sound-absorbing coefficient.

Figure 10. (a) acoustic foam, (b) ES PVDF/acoustic foam.

Figure 11. Sound-absorbing coefficient for various PVDF acoustic foam samples.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, porous piezoelectric PVDF materials were prepared by ES process, and effects of piezoelectric properties on the sound-absorbing were explored. Based on the experimental results, the conclusions are addressed as below:

1. ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes were successfully prepared by ES process. ES nanofiber membranes enhanced the area density and provided more changes for contacting with sound energy in the ES nanofiber membranes which contributed to more loss of sound energy by the friction and vibration of the internal nanofibers. ES nanofiber membranes absorbed in middle frequency region.
2. ES PVDF/CNT nanofiber membranes showed higher β -phase crystallinity and better piezoelectric properties.
3. The piezoelectric ES PVDF samples played an important role in converting the sound energy to electric potential and absorbed the sound wave in low frequency region.
4. Addition of CNT improves the piezoelectric properties and thus shifts the sound absorption to lower frequency region. The results proved that a good sound-absorption material was developed.
5. By using the friction and vibration behaviors of the sound absorbing materials and shunt-damping in piezoelectric PVDF, the ES PVDF/acoustic foam has a potential to be widely used as an efficient sound absorber in practical situations because of its good absorption performance in particular at low and middle frequency.

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